

DIVERSIFICATION OF PLANT-SPECIFIC GLYCOSYLTRANSFERASE IN ARCHAEPLASTIDA

ABSTRACT

Glycosyltransferases (GTs) are ubiquitous enzymes that catalyze glycosidic bond formation and play essential roles in nearly all aspects of cell biology. Despite their functional importance, the evolutionary origins and diversification of plant GT families remain poorly understood. Here, we investigated the distribution and evolutionary history of 41 GT families across 51 Archaeplastida genomes, spanning glaucophytes, red and green algae, and land plants. Our analyses revealed that only five GT families are conserved across all Archaeplastida, while most families expanded differentially, with a marked increase in embryophytes. Eight families originated specifically in charophyte algae, supporting their role as key precursors in the emergence of land plants. Subcellular localization predictions showed a preferential expansion of Golgi-resident GTs, particularly families GT1, GT2, GT4, GT8, GT31, GT47, and GT61, underscoring their link to plant cell wall (PCW) biosynthesis. Gene expansions correlated with genome size, indicating that duplication and polyploidization events were major drivers of GT diversification. Taken together, our results suggest that PCW complexity and the diversification of GT families were already underway in charophytes, providing critical structural and metabolic innovations that enabled the colonization of terrestrial environments. This study sheds new light on the evolutionary dynamics of GTs and highlights their central role in the transition from aquatic algae to land plants.

INTRODUCTION

Archaeplastida is a major clade of photosynthetic eukaryotes that includes land plants (Embryophyta) and several algal groups, such as Chlorophyta, Charophyta, Rhodophyta, and Glaucophyta. This clade originated from a primary endosymbiotic event in which a eukaryotic ancestor engulfed a cyanobacterium, giving rise to plastids and enabling oxygenic photosynthesis (Archibald, 2015; Ponce-Toledo *et al.*, 2017; Strasser *et al.*, 2021). This event represents one of the most transformative milestones in the history of life, driving the ecological success of Archaeplastida and their central role in global primary production (Raven & Edwards, 2001; Delwiche & Cooper, 2015). Among them, land plants stand out for having successfully colonized terrestrial habitats, a transition that reshaped ecosystems and opened new evolutionary trajectories (Kenrick & Crane, 1997; Jiao *et al.*, 2020).

A key innovation underlying this transition was the evolution of the plant cell wall (PCW), a dynamic and complex structure that provides mechanical support, regulates growth, and mediates interactions with the environment. Beyond structural integrity, PCWs conferred tolerance to desiccation, ultraviolet radiation, and fluctuations in water availability, while also facilitating symbio despite their recognized importance, the deep evolutionary origins and the major diversification events of GT families in Archaeplastida remain poorly understood.

In this work, we use a phylogenomic approach to investigate the evolutionary history of plant GT families, focusing on their origin, diversification, and expansion across Archaeplastida. By correlating the distribution of GT genes with the emergence of key lineages, we aim to uncover the molecular basis of PCW innovations that enabled plants to overcome the challenges of terrestrialization—mechanical support out of water, desiccation resistance, morphological plasticity, and ultimately, the remarkable ecological and morphological diversity of land plants. tic associations and immune responses (Showalter, 1993; Caffall & Mohnen, 2009; de Vries *et al.*, 2021). Structural modifications and increasing biochemical complexity of the PCW were associated with major evolutionary innovations, from the emergence of embryophytes to the development of vascular tissues, seeds, flowers, and fruits (Kenrick & Crane, 1997; Bowman *et al.*, 2019; Zhong *et al.*, 2019).

At the molecular level, the biosynthesis of polysaccharides is orchestrated by glycosyltransferases (GTs), enzymes that catalyze the transfer of activated sugar donors to acceptor substrates, forming glycosidic bonds (Lairson *et al.*, 2008). Plant GTs synthesize cellulose, hemicelluloses, and pectins, as well as glycoproteins, glycolipids, hormones, and

secondary metabolites such as flavonoids (Keegstra & Raikhel, 2001; Höfte & Voxeur, 2017). This dual role—structural and metabolic—was crucial for the diversification of plant form and function. In particular, the evolution of GT families involved in hemicellulose and pectin biosynthesis enabled modifications in wall architecture, allowing fine-tuned responses to mechanical and water stress, desiccation tolerance, and symbiotic interactions (Scheller & Ulvskov, 2010; Pauly & Keegstra, 2016; Zhang *et al.*, 2025).

Comparative genomic studies have shown that GT families expanded significantly during plant evolution, particularly in streptophyte algae and land plants, supporting the hypothesis that gene duplications, neofunctionalization, and horizontal gene transfer contributed to their diversification (Bowles *et al.*, 2022; Taujale *et al.*, 2020). However, despite their recognized importance, the evolutionary origins and major diversification events of GT families in Archaeplastida remain poorly understood.

In this work, we investigate the evolutionary history of plant GT families, focusing on their origin, diversification, and expansion across Archaeplastida. By correlating the distribution of GT genes with the emergence of key lineages, we aim to uncover the molecular basis of PCW innovations that enabled plants to overcome the challenges of terrestrialization—mechanical support out of water, desiccation resistance, morphological plasticity, and ultimately, the remarkable ecological and morphological diversity of land plants.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

Datasets

A complete set of predicted proteomes of Archaeplastida was obtained up to April 2023 from the CAZy database. A total of 51 proteomes were used in our analyses (Table 2). The predicted protein sets of charophytes, chlorophytes, embryophytes, rhodophytes, and glaucophytes were downloaded and used to generate local databases for BLAST searches (Altschul *et al.*, 1997). We assessed the completeness of all predicted proteomes using BUSCO version 5.4.5 (Simão *et al.*, 2015) with the *eukaryota_odb10* dataset. Figure S1 illustrates the distribution of BUSCO scores across different Archaeplastida lineages, while detailed information for each species can be found in Table S2.

Identification of GT proteins

Identification of GT-coding genes was performed through BLASTp, using the complete set of *Arabidopsis thaliana* protein sequences for each GT family (41 families in total) as queries to identify homologous genes in complete genomes and assembled transcriptomes. An e-value cutoff of $1e-5$ was used. Positive BLASTp hits were analyzed for the presence of characteristic GT structural domains with Pfam (version 31.0; <http://pfam.xfam.org/>) for each protein family (Table 3), employing HMMER 3.3.2 (<http://hmmmer.org/>) with the default cutoff. Target organism sequences were retrieved using samtools, and redundancy was reduced with the skipredundant program from EMBOSS 6.6.0.0, collapsing proteins with 100% identity to the longest isoform. Sequences were then manually inspected to remove remaining isoforms from the same gene, retaining only the longest protein encoded by each locus. Partial sequences shorter than 70% of the shortest *A. thaliana* sequence in the corresponding family were excluded to avoid compromising subsequent global alignments. Custom Python scripts used in this pipeline will be made publicly available on GitHub.

Statistical Analyses

Statistical analyses were performed using R software version 3.6.2 (<https://www.R-project.org/>). Graphs were constructed with the R packages *readxl*, *tidyverse*, *reshape2*, *tidyr*, *ggpubr*, *ggplot2*, *factoextra*, *FactoMineR*, and *scale*.

Subcellular Localization

To investigate whether GT function is linked to the formation of new families and their expansions, the GT proteins identified in the 52 Archaeplastida genomes were analyzed with DeepLoc 2 to predict their likely subcellular localization. This software uses deep learning and neural network algorithms to assign protein localization.

Phylogenetic Analyses

Protein sequence alignments were performed with MAFFT v7 using the following parameters: --thread 10, --reorder, --leavegappyregion, --maxiterate 1000, --retree 1, --localpair, --reorder. Alignments were used for subsequent phylogenetic analyses conducted with the maximum likelihood method implemented in IQ-TREE 2.6 on the SAGARANA HPC cluster (CEPAD-ICB-UFGM). The initial phylogenetic tree was calculated with BIONJ (Neighbor-Joining method) and optimized with the NNI (Nearest Neighbour Interchanges)

search method. Statistical support for nodes was assessed with the SH-like approximate likelihood ratio test (SH-aLRT) using 1000 replicates. Tree visualizations were made with FigTree.

Table 1. List of databases containing the predicted complete proteomes used in this study.

Specie	Local
<i>Arabidopsis thaliana</i>	https://data.jgi.doe.gov/refine-download/phytozome?organism=Athaliana&expanded=167
<i>Populus trichocarpa</i>	https://data.jgi.doe.gov/refine-download/phytozome?organism=Ptrichocarpa&expanded=533
<i>Sorghum bicolor</i>	https://data.jgi.doe.gov/refine-download/phytozome?organism=Sbicolor&expanded=454
<i>Oryza sativa</i>	https://data.jgi.doe.gov/refine-download/phytozome?organism=Osativa&expanded=323
<i>Selaginella moellendorffii</i>	https://data.jgi.doe.gov/refine-download/phytozome?organism=Smoellendorffii&expanded=91
<i>Physcomitrella patens</i>	https://data.jgi.doe.gov/refine-download/phytozome?organism=Ppatens&expanded=318
<i>Marchantia polymorpha</i>	https://data.jgi.doe.gov/refine-download/phytozome?organism=Mpolymorpha&expanded=320
<i>Anthoceros angustus</i>	https://datadryad.org/stash/dataset/doi:10.5061/dryad.msbcc2ftv
<i>Mesotaenium endlicherianum</i>	https://figshare.com/articles/dataset/Genomes_of_subaerial_Zygnematophyceae_provide_insights_into_land_plant_evolution/9911876/1
<i>Spirogloea muscicola</i>	https://figshare.com/articles/dataset/Genomes_of_subaerial_Zygnematophyceae_provide_insights_into_land_plant_evolution/9911876/1
<i>Chara braunii</i>	https://bioinformatics.psb.ugent.be/gdb/Chara_braunii/
<i>Klebsormidium nitens</i>	http://www.plantmorphogenesis.bio.titech.ac.jp/~algae_genome_project/klebsormidium/kf_download.htm
<i>Chlorokybus atrophyticus</i>	https://ftp.cngb.org/pub/CNSA/data1/CNP0000228/CNS0021447/CNA0002353/
<i>Mesostigma viride</i>	https://ftp.cngb.org/pub/CNSA/data1/CNP0000228/CNS0021438/CNA0002352/
<i>Volvox carteri</i>	https://data.jgi.doe.gov/refine-download/phytozome?organism=Vcarteri&expanded=167

	ed=317
<i>Chlamydomonas reinhardtii</i>	https://data.jgi.doe.gov/refine-download/phytozome?organism=Creinhardtii&expanded=281
<i>Monoraphidium neglectum</i>	https://genome.jgi.doe.gov/portal/pages/dynamicOrganismDownload.jsf?organism=Monneg1
<i>Gonium pectorale</i>	https://genome.jgi.doe.gov/portal/pages/dynamicOrganismDownload.jsf?organism=Gonpec1
<i>Dunaliella salina</i>	https://genome.jgi.doe.gov/portal/pages/dynamicOrganismDownload.jsf?organism=Dunsal1
<i>Picochlorum sp.</i>	https://genome.jgi.doe.gov/portal/pages/dynamicOrganismDownload.jsf?organism=Picsp_1
<i>Chlorella variabilis</i> NC64A	https://genome.jgi.doe.gov/portal/pages/dynamicOrganismDownload.jsf?organism=ChINC64A_1
<i>Coccomyxa subellipsoidea</i> C-169	https://genome.jgi.doe.gov/portal/Coc_C169_1/Coc_C169_1.download.ftp.html
<i>Auxenochlorella protothecoides</i>	https://genome.jgi.doe.gov/portal/pages/dynamicOrganismDownload.jsf?organism=Auxeprot1
<i>Ostreococcus tauri</i>	https://genome.jgi.doe.gov/portal/pages/dynamicOrganismDownload.jsf?organism=Ostta4221_3
<i>Ostreococcus lucimarinus</i>	https://data.jgi.doe.gov/refine-download/phytozome?organism=Olucimarinus&expanded=231
<i>Micromonas pusilla</i> - CCMP1545	https://genome.jgi.doe.gov/portal/pages/dynamicOrganismDownload.jsf?organism=MicpuC3v2
<i>Micromonas commoda</i> RCC299	https://genome.jgi.doe.gov/portal/pages/dynamicOrganismDownload.jsf?organism=MicpuN3v2
<i>Bathycoccus prasinus</i>	https://genome.jgi.doe.gov/portal/pages/dynamicOrganismDownload.jsf?organism=Batpra1
<i>Galdieria sulphuraria</i>	http://plants.ensembl.org/Galdieria_sulphuraria/Info/Index
<i>Cyanidioschyzon merolae</i>	http://plants.ensembl.org/Cyanidioschyzon_merolae/Info/Index
<i>Chondrus crispus</i>	http://plants.ensembl.org/Chondrus_crispus/Info/Annotation/#assembly
<i>Cyanophora paradoxa</i>	http://cyanophora.rutgers.edu/cyanophora/blast.php

Table 2. List of Pfam domains used to define each of the GT families

Family	Domain	ID
GT 1	Glyco_trans_1_3	PF13528.9
	Glyco_trans_1_4	PF13528.9.9
	UDPGT	PF00201.21
GT2	Cellulose_synt	PF03552.17
	Glycos_transf_2	PF00535.29
	Glyco_tranf_2_3	PF13641.9
GT4	Glyco_transf_4	PF13439.9
	Glyco_trans_4_2	PF13477.9
	Glyco_trans_4_4	PF13579.9
	Glyco_trans_4_5	PF16994.8
	Sucrose_synt	PF00862.22
GT5	Glyco_transf_5	PF08323.14
GT8	Glyco_transf_8	PF01501.23
	Mannosyl_trans3	PF11051.11
GT10	Glyco_transf_10	PF00852.22
GT13	GNT-I	PF03071.18
GT14	Branch	PF02485.24
GT16	MGAT2	PF05060.17
GT17	Glyco_transf_17	PF04724.16
GT19	LpxB	PF02684.18
GT20	Glyco_transf_20	PF00982.24
GT22	Glyco_transf_22	PF03901.20
GT24	Glyco_transf_24	PF18404.4
GT28	Glyco_transf_28	PF03033.23
	Glyco_tran_28_C	PF04101.19
	MGDG_synt	PF06925.14
GT29	Glyco_transf_29	PF00777.21
GT30	Glycos_transf_N	PF04413.19

GT31	Galactosyl_T	PF01762.24
GT32	Gb3_synth	PF04572.15
GT33	Glycos_transf_1	PF00534.23
	Glyco_transf_4	PF13439.9
GT34	Glyco_transf_34	PF05637.15
GT35	Phosphorylase	PF00343.23
GT37	XG_FTase	PF03254.16
GT41	Glyco_transf_41	PF13844.9
GT43	Glyco_transf_43	PF03360.18
GT47	Exostosin	PF03016.18
GT48	Glucan_synthase	PF02364.18
GT50	Mannosyl_trans	PF05007.16
GT57	Alg6_Alg8	PF03155.18
GT58	ALG3	PF05208.15
GT59	DIE2_ALG10	PF04922.15
GT61	Glyco_transf_61	PF04577.17
GT64	Glyco_transf_64	PF09258.13
GT66	STT3	PF02516.17
GT75	RGP	PF03214.16
GT76	Mannosyl_trans2	PF04188.16
GT77	Nucleotid_trans	PF03407.19
GT90	Glyco_transf_90	PF05686.15
GT92	Glyco_transf_92	PF01697.30
GT95	It has no known GT domain but activity has been demonstrated experimentally	
GT96	It has no known GT domain but activity has been demonstrated experimentally	

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Distribution of GT Families in Archaeplastida

A total of 458 *Arabidopsis thaliana* protein sequences, previously classified into 41 GT families by the CAZy database (<http://www.cazy.org/>), were used as queries for BLASTp searches in a database composed of 51 complete genomes belonging to the main clades of Archaeplastida (Figure 1). The distribution of the number of genes per family varied significantly among the GT families and the Archaeplastida genomes (Figure 1A). More families and genes were found in land plants (Embryophyta) than in non-Viridiplantae algae. In red algae, 31 of the 41 GT families found in land plants were detected. The analysis showed that Cyanophora has the greatest reduction observed in the repertoire and quantity of GTs. Previously, molecular studies suggested that Glaucophyta is the group most closely related to Viridiplantae and Rhodophyta, being the clade with the deepest branching within Archaeplastida (Lee *et al.*, 2016; Ferrari *et al.*, 2019). However, we now know that Rhodophyta is the most basal group (Bowles *et al.*, 2022). The reduced repertoire in glaucophytes can be explained by events of GT family loss. The GT families vary widely in terms of the total number of genes (Figure 1B) and were largely dominated by Viridiplantae (Figure 1C), showing that green plants have a broader repertoire of GT enzymes than red algae and glaucophytes, due to the increased biochemical diversity of polysaccharides. The GT1 family had the largest number of GT genes (Figure 1B), found in all clades (Figure 1C) but not in all species (Figure 1A). The same applies to the GT47 family, which had the second-largest number of genes. The GT1, GT2, GT5, GT20, and GT77 families were the only ones found in all species (Figure 1A). Few examples of GT family loss were found among the analysed land plant genomes: *Pinus sylvestris* lost genes from the GT96 and GT33 families, *Ginkgo biloba* lost genes from the GT64, GT37, GT58, GT59, and GT30 families, and *Gnetum montanum* lost genes from the GT36 and GT76 families (Figure 1A). The GT30 family was lost in *Cycas micholitzii*, as well as in *Gnetum montanum* and *Ginkgo biloba*. All 41 GT families analysed were detected in at least one species of charophyte (Figure 1A, 1B, and 1C). Our results indicate that only five families are found in all Archaeplastida groups, suggesting that approximately 90% of the GT families identified in *Arabidopsis* are not conserved across Archaeplastida (Figure 1). The conserved families are likely essential for the basic processes carried out by all Archaeplastida cells.

Gene Distribution and Frequencies of GT Families in Archaeplastida

The distribution of the total number of genes, its frequencies, and the number of GT families present in Archaeplastida are illustrated in Figure 2. There is an expansion in the number of GT genes in genomes, as groups acquire greater metabolic complexity and adapt to terrestrial environments (C3, C4, CAM??). In the genomes from land plants, a higher quantity and frequency of GT genes, as well as greater diversity in the number of GT families, were found. As expected, the clade Embryophyta exhibited significant differences compared to all other Archaeplastida groups in the distribution of GT genes

Comparing genomes within the plant lineage, we find that the number of protein-coding genes in these genomes increases, as the total number of GT genes also increases (Figure 2D), as does the frequency of GT genes per genome (Figure 2E), and the number of GT families in each Archaeplastida (Figure 2F). The correlations observed were positive, suggesting that there may have been positive selective pressure on gene duplication and the emergence of new GT gene families throughout the evolutionary history of these organisms. The significant increase in the number of GT genes and families in the plant lineage can be explained by genomic duplications, which are common in land plants due to polyploidization events.

The subcellular location

The results demonstrate the main cellular compartments in which these proteins were found. Subcellular localization can be used in inferring the likely function of a GT. Subcellular localization prediction analysis showed that the evolution of GTs in plants was guided by the expansion of the number of genes encoding enzymes potentially resident in the Golgi apparatus. The proportion of proteins predicted in each subcellular compartment by group is shown in Figure 4. We can see a pattern, that the number of proteins in the Golgi complex begins to increase, from chlorophytes to charophytes, and this number increases even more in terrestrial plants (Figure 3). The amount of GT proteins placed in the Golgi apparatus is: 18.8% for Rhodophyta/Glaucophyta, 15.1% for Chlorophyta, 19.4% for Charophyta, 29.2% for Angiosperms and 30% for cryptogamic Embryophytes. The main families responsible for this expansion are: GT1, GT2, GT4, GT8, GT31, GT47, GT61. This leads us to conclude that the expansion of the number of GT genes is linked to PCW synthesis. We observed that proteins targeted to the Golgi complex did not show significant targeting for other

compartments, while the proportion of proteins in the cytoplasm and endoplasmic reticulum decreases slightly. In the Golgi complex, expansion throughout the groups is even greater among angiosperms. The evolution of GTs in plants was guided by the preferential expansion of proteins located in the Golgi and this strongly suggests that this is where cell wall synthesis occurs, one of the main drivers of plant evolution.

Using the 51 proteomes, phylogenetic and structural analyzes in terms of functional domains are being produced for each of the 41 families of GTs in order to confirm the homology of these proteins. Phylogenetic analyzes will help to understand the functional diversification of each of these families.

Preliminary evidence suggests a major event of increased PCV complexity occurred before the emergence of land plants. This may be evidence of terrestrialization of charophyte algae prior to the emergence of embryophytes. This new hypothesis suggests that embryophytes would have emerged on dry land from terrestrial charophyte algae (Harholt *et al.*, 2016; Del Bem 2018). This would be related to the evolution of so many PCV elements associated with life on dry land in the same evolutionary time period.

Conclusion

In this study, we investigated the deep origin and major diversification events of glycosyltransferase (GT) families within the Archaeplastida clade. Our results demonstrate that, while only a small set of GT families is conserved across all groups, the vast majority underwent differential expansion throughout evolutionary history, with a marked enrichment in land plants. This expansion is strongly correlated with the increasing complexity of the plant cell wall, particularly for genes encoding Golgi apparatus-localized proteins. This suggests that GT diversification was a key driver of the structural innovations required for the transition to life on land.

The positive correlation between the number of GT genes and families and overall genome size indicates that gene duplication and polyploidization events were central to the diversification of these enzymes. Furthermore, the evidence of cell wall complexity already present in charophyte algae supports the hypothesis that critical adaptations for terrestrialization originated prior to the emergence of embryophytes.

Collectively, our findings provide new insights into the evolution of the biosynthetic machinery for polysaccharides and glycoconjugates in Archaeplastida, highlighting glycosyltransferases as pivotal elements in the adaptation to terrestrial environments. These results not only deepen our understanding of plant cell wall evolution but also pave the way for future comparative and biotechnological studies aimed at exploring the functional diversity of GTs across different plant lineages.

A

Figure 1. Repertoires of GT families for the main lineages of Archaeplastida. (A) Balloon plot showing the distribution of the number of GTs for each of the Archaeplastida genomes relative to each of the families of GTs. Distribution of (B) number of genes and (C) gene frequencies of each of the GT families in Archaeplastida.

Figure 2. Distribution and qualitative comparison of GTs in Archaeplastida clades. (A) Distribution of gene counts, (B) gene frequencies, and (C) number of GT families per genome in the main Archaeplastida clades. The dark lines in the boxes indicate medians, the width of the boxes is the IQR, the lowest and highest values within 1.5 times the IQR of the first and third quartiles. Positive correlations: (D) between number of GT genes and total number of genes in the Archaeplastida genome; (E) between number of GT genes and frequencies of GT genes per genome in Archaeplastida and (F) between number of GT genes and number of GT families in Archaeplastida.

Figure 3. Number of predicted proteins in each subcellular compartment per group. In this figure we can observe the number of proteins predicted in each subcellular compartment.

Figure 4. Proportion of predicted proteins in each subcellular compartment by group. In this figure we can observe the proportion of predicted proteins in each subcellular compartment.

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